

3. Soft Skills have a great impact on the effectiveness of a person's professional, social, and personal life activities.

4. Not related to the specifics of professional activity, but is the same for different types of professional activities.

5. Formation and development of flexible skills of students is the main indicator of adaptation in the conditions of today's demands and rapidly changing society.

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4. KS Yermeev. Directions for improving educational work with students in the context of digital transformation of society

PENALTIES AND INCENTIVES IN THE SCHOOL REGULATIONS OF THE BULGARIAN AND GREEK EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN VARNA OF THE 70s OF THE XIX CENTURY TO THE 20s OF THE XX CENTURY

Veselin Dimitrov Mihalev

Ph.D

Varna Free University „Chernorizetz Hrabar”

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Abstract

The problem of the application of the system of penalties and incentives in the Bulgarian and Greek schools in Varna is not sufficiently researched in the scientific and pedagogical literature, because of that, in some school regulations are given only penalties to students, and the incentives are hardly affected. In the current post is made an attempt for the source of knowledge in pedagogical research of archival historical documents in the Bulgarian language and in the Greek language, proving the school's practice of educational institutions surveyed penalties and incentives of the students. The study aims to outline, on the one hand, the scope of the diversity and, on the other hand, the various forms of educational impact associated with their application during the researched period.

Keywords: encouragement, punishment, school, teacher, students, teaching, disciplinary regulations, discipline.

*„The best remedy of education is the hope of reward and the fear of penalty”
Sava Dobroplodni*

1. INTRODUCTION

The first written school regulations that regulate issues relating to penalties and incentives in the Bulgarian schools and in the Greek schools in Varna date back to the beginning of the 70s of the XX century. They are developed by teachers and members of school boards. Their introduction is the result of a conscious need of regulated rules and prohibitions in order to improve the school order. To achieve the aims of the pedagogical research, instruments were applied to which are generally accepted in the context of pedagogical methods in historiography – archiving method, facta – graphic method, history of our birthplace method and research of school documentation relating to the activity of the educational institutions in Varna during the period.

2. PENALTIES AND INCENTIVES IN BULGARIAN SCHOOLS

An important means of educational impact on students' behavior in the public – church Bulgarian school

in Varna in 70s of the XIX century are „**falagata**” and „**penalty plates**” with inscriptions: „*liar*”, „*thief*”, „*disturber*”, „*fool*” and „*careless*”. The use of „**falagata**” as an attribute of education appears to be primarily mean for impact. The punishment of public - church students by „**falagata**” bears the mark of medieval strictness. This simple and terrible thing often strikes genuine horror and it is used for tying the feet of the student who is beaten. For the fear of its applying the public - church students in Varna sincerely share: „*When we looked at it - „falagata”, it was creeping us out*” (Cerov, 1914: p. 9). The student who is punished by his mutual teacher depending on the severity of the misconduct must stand with hanging „**penalty plate**” on his neck for a certain time, facing students and in many cases he is escorted by his classmates around the streets of the city. According to I. Cerov, this punishment has a strong impact on personality education of adolescents.

In his pedagogical activity the teacher Sava Dobroplodni harshly condemns the fight as a penal mean and he is convinced that: „*the best remedy of education is the hope of reward and the fear of penalty*”. For the

penalties which are taken and associated with providing of discipline of the mutual students in Varna, he explains: „it was not allowed to outrage because they were observed and punished by overseer" (Cerov, 1914: p.9).

For the impact of penalties to guilty students he is deeply convinced that the teacher must observe certain pedagogical measure: „Neither penalties shall not destroy them, nor shall make them as cattle". S. Dobroplodni raises his view of the upbringing with the words: „the best system for the nurture and upbringing is when man use sweet speeches and nonviolent means." Despite his confidence in it, he never stops asking himself rhetorical question: „but if only they can tame the hard and sturdy character of children?" (Dobroplodni, 1852: p.70).

In 1862/1863 for the first time in mutual Bulgarian school in Varna he introduces **three grades** in the scale of the assessment of the behavior of the students: „**reprehensible**", „**lower**" and „**commendable**" which along with the conducting annual examinations and awarding the best with incentive rewards are part of those classical forms that he leaves as the pedagogical heritage. The placement of the highest mark for behavior of mutual students - „**commendable**" by its nature is seen as a kind of encouragement to students, who according to his requirements must „**with zeal come to school**". With the applying of class - lesson organization of training in the Bulgarian school is introduced **four - grade** scale to assess the behavior of the students by their teachers: „**reprehensible**", „**low**", „**medium**", and „**commendable**" (Tonev 1962, p.135). The behavior of students, assessed as „**commendable**" is considered the highest level of incentive.

The assessment of the behavior of the students attending in the school practice of class (high school) educational institutions in Varna by the end of the XIX century. There are certain requirements for their behavior and humility, which are recorded in the school regulations.

In the end of the XIX century in the school regulations of the Varna State High School for girls „Marie Louise" and in the Varna State High School for men „Ferdinand I" introduce **six - grade** scale for evaluating the behavior of high school students: „**exemplary**", „**commendable**", „**good**", „**medium**", „**reproached**" and „**bad**" (GVDDG, 1897: p.178, GVDMG, 1897: p.34). In a comparative analysis of the behavior of high school students from the first grade of the Varna State High School for girls "Marie Louise" during the period of 1897/1898. is established following result from the evaluation of their behavior: „**exemplary**" - 50 %, „**commendable**" - 18 %, „**good**" - 18,4 %, „**medium**" - 7,8 %, „**reproached**" - 3,5 %, and „**bad**" - 2,3 %.

Research of school documentation during the period of 1909/1910 shows the behavior of boys in the Varna State High School for men "Ferdinand I" is assessed in five - grades scale: „**exemplary**" - 67%, „**commendable**" - 17%, „**good**" - 11%, „**medium**" - 2%, „**reproached**" - 3 % (GVDMG, 1910: p.34).

In the disciplinary regulation from 1906 of the Varna State High School for girls „Maria -Luisa" is

manifested a negative behavior of students and it is provided for imposing the most severe disciplinary measure „**expulsion**" by giving parents of punished school girls a chance to appeal against the decision of the teachers' board in front of the Ministry of public enlightenment (GVDDG, 1906: p.28, 57).

Students who have mastered the course material, during the conduct of the annual exams in front of their parents and public are granted a certain type of incentive rewards – *books and small pictures*. Some of those classical forms represent eternal inherently pedagogical heritage and allow their applying in modern educational practice of the contemporary Bulgarian school.

A form used for education and stimulating the „diligence" and the moral qualities of mutual students in Varna in 70s of the XIX century is the awarding of medal „**order of praise**", which is a type of incentive reward. Most of the diligent students are given **diplomas** with inscriptions: „*diligent*", „*gentle*" and „*reasonable*". The Diploma as distinctive sign is given as incentive to award student as to serve as an example to the others. The names of the best students and those who „**with zeal come to school**" are given special „**tables of honor**".

The teacher, according to S. Dobroplodni, must know the individual characteristics of each student and he must approach to each student differently. In 1863/1864, 12 students of the Class Bulgarian school receive awards for „*humility and good conduct*" from the head teacher S. Dobroplodni. In the determination of this application he pays particular attention if the student comes to school with „*zeal*". Indicative in this aspect is the fact that in 1874 in Varna Class School „*St. St. Cyril and Methodius*" at the end of the annual exams the student Radi Petrov receives certificate stating: „*Award for success, good behavior and humility - 1874*".

For the principle of the applying of the incentive awards Dobroplodni convinced writes: „*Awards must be such, so they do not make students stupid, proud and so on*". According to him, the teacher should always awards kindness and punishes evil. But any „*reward or punishment should be done with righteousness, let no one be favored. Dignity and sanity must be hailed and rewarded. And when the teacher gives reward and punishment he must be fair*" (Dobroplodni, 1852: p.71-73). His philosophy for education of adolescents comes down to the ability to attract their love and to teach them in virtues as reverence and respect, but not in fear because of the punishment itself but the consciousness and belief that this will make them better. His outlooks on education of students are found in his thoughts: „*The teacher should always rewards good and punishes evil*".

The praise of the students in front of their parents and the public is a kind of encouragement which in particular way is directed to classmates and attending at the annual exams. In this aspect in commendation of the „superior" Varna's students, who are taught in the Bulgarian Class School, S. Dobroplodni reads their names in front of an audience at the end of the annual exams, which has a strong disciplinary effect on promoting of the student personality.

3. PENALTIES AND INCENTIVES IN GREEK SCHOOLS

The main mean of ensuring order and discipline in the public - church Greek schools in Varna in 70s of the XIX century as well as in Bulgarian schools is „**falagata**”. This fact proves that the body punishment in these schools are not forbidden as well. There are many memories proving that it is used as a tool for body punishments and as a mean for re - education: „*Falagata was suspended and was hanging over above the heads of the children, more threatening even than Sword of Damocles*” (IVAD, 1914: p.57). From this text it is known that its use by teachers as an „attribute” is the only correctional mean.

Proofs of applying of this body punishment in the Greek public - church schools in the second half of the XIX century are memories of Varna’s citizens, contemporaries of the Greek public - church enlightenment, published in the „Announcements of Varna archeological association”. They share: „*Writing in Greek schools is usually after the Psalter with translation in Greek: „Start my hand good, write good letters not to be beaten and to be grounded and fall in falagata. Winter time, every morning, the students wore a piece of wood for the stove and when they went home every night, they recited in Greek language: "I honor my father with dedication, I respect my mother, I am obedient for each order of my first brother, my sister and my father. Love each other, be God - fearing, respect the King, show reverence to priests. A person who is illiterate is a fruitless tree. The teaching is more valuable than gold and silver. Good night, benign master of us. And tomorrow who does not came early, to small ones - 12 rods, to the big ones - 24, to the protoshol¹ - 48 and two more on top for the felicitation. All fifty. Amen*”.

Ensuring the order and the discipline of the students in the Greek schools in Varna is a part of the duties of the Greek teachers. Any their offence is sanctioned with the appropriate penalty. Student who with his actions violate the established order, receives „**penalty plates**” with inscription: „*chatter*”, „*sloppy*” and „*disobedient*”. Other applicable **penalties** associated with the negative behavior of the students in the process of self – teaching organization boil down to: *relocation of student in the lower group, punished student copy parts of a book and writing down the name of a student at the „Board of dishonor*”. Those penalties applied in the Greek mutual schools contribute to forming qualities and virtues in adolescents - humility, wisdom, and diligence and their implementation aims ridiculing their negative actions.

In the 70s of the XIX century for the first time in the school's practice of the classrooms of the Greek educational institutions, like Bulgarian educational institutions, is introduced **evaluation of behavior** for the students. There are many cases in which students do not come for the annual tests because of various reasons

and it affects to the assessment of their behavior, which is valued as „*bad*”.

The school tutor Y. Floris² in 1864 reports for negative behavior shown by the Greek students from the initial grades in extended report which is translated from Greek to Bulgarian. In it he shares with concern for the problems associated with their negative behavior: „*I Can express my dissatisfaction with the fact that on these annual exams, we have students who do not wish to appear for one reason or another, whose conduct will be announced in the beginning of the following year as "poor" and to be known by all, that school is not a place for entertainment but a place where knowledge and personality are formed*” (ΔΑ-Βάρνη, 82 κ ωπ. 1 α. ε. 25, 1-3; 7-8).

In 1891 Haralampos Lambridis³ - headmaster of the Greek three - grades school for man, he also shares about existence of personal problems in the relationship between boys and these problems are a consequence of their negative behavior. From the exported information in his report to the members of the Greek community and the school board it is clear that according to him, students from the second grade admit absences which are result of inaction and passivity of their parents. It is also dictated by their unwilling to hear negative assessments about the behavior of their children. As a result, he takes cardinal measures and he aims to improve the discipline of some students who he reports for in his report to the school board. He says: „*For proper “treatment” I offer quite “effective drug” and I mean total termination of the training of the students in the second grade, although I realize that some students with excellent behavior and morals will be turned into victims, but for the sake of the overall improvement of discipline I'm ready for such a step*”.

In the early years of the XIX century the whole organization of training in the Greek educational institutions (mutual, initial and class) in Varna is governed by an important prescriptive document from 31. I. 1901 whose content is translated from Greek language to Bulgarian language and it is titled: *Πειθαρχικός των Βάρνη κανονισμός εν Ελληνικών Σχολών* (Disciplinary regulation of the Greek schools in Varna), containing 47 articles and also it is signed by the Varna Greek municipality and the Board of the Greek Trustees of the Greek schools. Its introduction into the school practice is dictated by the conscious need to impose clear regulations that govern certain obligations of students and if they are not met, they impose certain disciplinary sanctions.

This regulation manages placing of the **annual assessment for behavior** of students which according to article 47 is assessed in **five level scale**: „*model role*”, „*commendable*”, „*good*”, „*average*” and „*unsatisfactory*” (Πειθαρχικός των κανονισμός Βάρνη Σχολών Ελληνικών, 1901: p.8).

¹ Protoshol (from Greek) – student from the upper class.

² Yanaki Floris is a Bulgarian originally born in Dobrina, Varna. He is one of the prominent members of the Greek municipality in Varna. After his sudden death in his place as a school tutor is elected Eleftherios Pastias (Nikov, 1934: p.50).

³ Haralampos Lambridis - graduates the University of Theology in island Halki. In 1891 he is appointed as a Headmaster of the Greek school in Varna for men. On 26.VII.1891 retires, explaining the reasons for its decision to the school board (Οδησός 1891, issue 24, 29).

In this document are strictly defined various kinds of **penalties** of students who are in connection with the failure of their school obligations. Articles 36-37 regulate their duties outside of school. In the weekend after preparation of homework assignments, the student can afford in more „humble way" to have fun with his companions only if every one of them has proven moral behavior before. If he is seen in a place where he is not allowed to be and if he is in an "inappropriate environment" or he is with "inappropriate clothing", he will be given disciplinary action if necessary - „**publicly scolding**" by the Headmaster and if he does this again, he will be given a „**removal of school**".

Students who do not attend regular classes and assume absences are given severe penalties. In articles 13-16 define the cases in which they may take absences from school. In the document it is written that none of them have the right to be absent from school without valid excuse. When they admit 5 absences, they are punished with „**stern warning**" by the Headmaster. If a group of students who arbitrarily not present in the classroom, they are subject to stringent disciplinary sanctions and they have to be imposed by the Headmaster and the school board.

The disciplinary regulation sets out the requirements that students must follow in their relations with the teachers and staff of the school. They are not allowed to come into conflict with the teacher, even with overseer but if they do that, there are two types of penalties - „**stern scolding**" and „**suspension from school from 5 to 8 days**".

In articles 22-23, school tutors take disciplinary measures in order of those students, who contribute to the destruction of the base in Greek schools. In cases where a student is found scratched on the walls of the classroom or in the school building if he damages the desks with a pocket knife and paint in places where it is not allowed or that inflicts certain material damage - broken windows, broken chair or desk, he will be given a first penalty - „**scolding**" by the Headmaster. When a student has been found for a second time to do this, he will be given „**temporary suspended from school**".

A special place in the disciplinary regulation is given to the **system for the imposition of disciplinary penalties** according to the type and severity of the student's foul. There are seven levels of penalties: *conversation „eye to eye" with the teacher or with the Headmaster, standing up, scolding of student by the teacher or by the headmaster in front of the entire class, multiple copy of mistaken learning task (that is in relation to the teaching material), closing of student in the classroom without the right to leave, public scolding by the Headmaster in front of the school board, temporary suspension of 5 to 8 educational days and expulsion*.

In imposing the worst penalty - „**expulsion from school**" it is necessary to get a decision of the teachers and the school board. Parents must be informed of the penalties and his name is written on a "blackboard" in the Headmaster's Office.

At the beginning of the XX century the organization of training in the Greek male and female high schools in Varna is carried out by the disciplinary regulations and they are established by training centers in

Greece, which represents adjusted basis for their management. One of them is: *Κανον της σχολείων των τριμύς εν Αθήνας* (Regulation of Greek high schools and secondary schools) from 1891. The fourth section of this document is titled: „*The basic rules for the evaluation of the school discipline and procedure for imposition of disciplinary penalties and stimulation of the high school students*" (*Κανονισμός της Αθήνας των σχολείων εν 1889*).

The behavior of high school students in the Greek schools in Varna at the end of the XIX century is estimated in **five level scale**: 10 - „*commendable*", 8 - „*decent*", 6 - „*respectable*", 4 - „*good*", 0 - „*bad*". The assessment of the conduct of the students covers visiting classes, as well as, good relationships. When high school student has received a score of 0 - „*bad*" he is punished with „**suspension from school**". Disciplinary sanctions of high school students also are imposed for some absences from school without appropriate reasons. In cases in which the high school student absents more than 25 hours of Greek language lessons or more than 20 hours in one of the subjects studied, as well as, if in the year he concedes over 100 absences because of apology or health reasons, he is not allowed to go to the annual exams in June. For „*minor violations*" such as unauthorized absences from students, as well as, conducts, a disciplinary action is required - „**reprimand**". For repeated violation there is another penalty: „**closing in a separate room from one to eight hours**", while he is in this room, the student writes self - criticizing texts to himself. If a student fails to correct his behavior and doesn't realize the consequences of his negative actions, he is punished with „**removal of teaching sessions from one to twenty days**" and it may be extended to six months by the teachers' board.

Students who violate the Disciplinary regulation of Greek schools, could be given the most severe disciplinary penalty - „**exclusion**" by both teachers board and by school board. The exclusion as a kind of penalty finds its expression in **three versions**: *exclusion from school, expulsion without the right of the student to continue his studies in another high school in the city, exclusion without the right of the student to train in educational establishment and put the student under police supervision*.

In the beginning of the XX century applying of the most severe disciplinary penalty - „**exclusion**" testifies a Protocol (5. III. 1903) from meeting of the Board of the teachers of Greek male high school in Varna, which discusses the poor behavior of a student (ΔΑ- Βάρνη, φ. 82 κ ωπ. 1 α. ε. 51, 201, 36, 37).

Incentives as a sort of reward to the students take an important place in the school's practice of Greek educational institutions during the researched period. From the text of the published memories of unknown citizens of Varna - contemporaries of Greek education in public - church schools in „*Notifications of the Varna archaeological society*" in 1914, it could be concluded that after the graduation of the public - church education the student also gets a type of incentive on the part of his parents: „*Greek school had no classes. With the completion of a book and changing it with another, the student was accompanied by the school to his*

father's house by the protoshol and his classmates. He was put down on a chair at home then he was thrown three times in the air, sitting on this chair and his classmates shouted "aksios" (worthy) and after this ritual they put him on the ground. Then the mother of the student **rewarded** the protoshol, she sat table on and fed them all, after that she accepted "greetings" of visitors, neighbors and relatives. The next day, the teacher is sent gifts by richer parents - suit and clothing and from poorer - rooster. That was it and it finished with examinations and **awards for success**" (IVAD, 1914: p.55).

An important element of the implementation of the self - teaching organization of training in each Greek schools in Varna is the introduction of a system of **incentive rewards**. The rewards aim to promote mutual students for their diligence and love for teaching. Those who learn well receive „**special tickets**”, which is the basis of the mutual teacher to reward the student and after student receives a few tickets, he gets the prize. The rewards represent paintings and small books. They aim to promote mutual students for their diligence and love for teaching. They receive a prize - **an emblem with the inscription in Greek**: „*worthy at reading*” or „*worthy at arithmetic*”. A well - established form of decorating is **getting numbers** which hang the buttons of clothes on of mutual students depending on their success, where on small planks is written the word „*first*”.

Another type of incentive in the mutual school practice of the Greek mutual schools is the awarding of **a medal „the order of merit”** which is collective and it is given to a group of students for their manifested diligence. The awarding of commendations to students boosts their diligence and humility in the process of education. Some of them are „**medals**” and the special „**Emblem of the Greek society**”. There is a proof of their applying in a report made by the school tutor Y. Floris. He presents it in front of the school board and the Greek municipality. He reports with satisfaction in it: „*With great joy and gratitude I give you a medal on which it is painted the name of each of you, as well as, the emblem of the Greek society*” (ΔΑ - Βάρνη, φ. 82 κ ωπ 1 α. ε. 25, 1, 3, 7, 8). Another form is the rewarding of the dutiful students of Greek classrooms schools with **books, paintings and small prizes**. A dedication note says that a book has been bought to a student by the school board in 1873. Οι τεχνιτών άνδρες μεγάλοι μικρών εκ. Σύγγραμμα Αντωνίου De Saint - Gervais (Great people of the little masters) by Antoine de Saint - Gervais, translated from French by S. Lambros, published in Greek in Athens (Todorov, Liberatos 2006: p.35).

At the beginning of the XX century in the Greek high schools in Varna also set incentives in the form of **praise**. Student who graduates with excellent marks will be mentioned publicly in front of classmates and the local Greek community. Besides the moral rewards, the school board provides material ones, too. They give students annual cash grants (Κανονισμός σχολείων της Αθήνας των 1889).

4. CONCLUSION

From the studies who are made searching into the pool of knowledge, we can make six **CONCLUSIONS**:

1. The main “method” for education and achieving of discipline in Bulgarian public – church schools and in Greek public - church schools in 70s of the XX century is connected with the imposition of the body punishments, which lead to humiliation of the student personality.

2. First school regulations in the researched educational institutions from the 70s of the XX century are testament to the existence of a conscious need of introduction of rules which can achieve a good school order. The enrichment of the arsenal of means to educate, applied in Greek and Bulgarian schools are aimed at creating models of a good personal example and high public moral. The expression of negative conduct related to non-compliance with obligations of the school and ignoring the prohibitions of the teachers is sanctioned with strict disciplinary sanctions. The penalty remains the primary method of education of adolescents to achieve the desired discipline, but changes in different varieties.

3. At the beginning of the XX century there is a trend for the presence of wide perimeter of differentiation of types of penalties for students who fail to comply with the statutory requirements. The main aim is finding the most accurate penalty, corresponding to the gravity of the their offense and in his order.

4. The choice of the type of penalty is carried out by different authorities, depending on the severity of the foul - the lightest are forced by the class teacher and more stringent - by the Headmaster and the school board as the management bodies.

5. The school documentation is used as a mean of recording the stiff penalties imposed on the students.

6. The incentive as the primary method of education in the Bulgarian National Renaissance Period presents in the studied written documents, relating to the activities of the Bulgarian schools in Varna, although it is applied very often in the educational practice. It is seen mostly in moral aspect by provided awards. This favors the formation of personality qualities in adolescents. The diligence and curiosity are awarded as well. The increased economic potential of local Greek municipality in Varna at the end of the XX century often allows providing the material type of incentives to students of Greek nationality. In the educational institutions there is a tendency to award the „superb” students to be applied almost always combined with excellent grades and behavior. The applying of the system of different types of incentives helps for practicing control over the behavior of students in the educational institutions.

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